

An Exploratory Study of Digital Literacy and Proficiency Challenges in Citizen-Based Initiatives

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Abstract—As citizen-based initiatives increasingly rely on data analytics systems to process crowdsourced data and generate actionable insights, digital proficiency and digital literacy are becoming critical factors in ensuring their success and impact. However, varying levels of digital proficiency, but also digital literacy, among non-expert participants present significant challenges in data processing, interpretation, and collaborative insight generation. This paper explores the key challenges related to digital literacy and proficiency in citizen-based initiatives, focusing on participants’ technological readiness, degree of data literacy, and the general usability of analytical tools in contexts where digital skills are limited. It also explores strategies to address these challenges, including targeted training programs and participatory approach for user-centered technology design. By addressing these challenges, the democratization of citizen-based initiatives can be improved, streamlining data-driven decision-making and maximizing their collective impact.

Keywords—digital literacy, digital proficiency, citizen-based initiatives, data analytics platforms.

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of citizen-based initiatives, combined with the growing demand for crowdsourced data, has dramatically expanded the role of data and data-driven approaches in shaping citizens’ everyday lives. This growing demand is largely driven by the limitations of existing authoritative observational networks and surveying campaigns, which, due to their limited coverage, often fail to provide comprehensive data required to fully investigate urban processes [1]. As a result, citizen-based initiatives have become increasingly applied in areas like environmental monitoring and urban development, where collective contributions from individuals serve to inform key decisions that impact communities on a local and global scale. For instance, widely adopted solution such as OpenStreetMap [2], where citizens contribute geographic data, have transformed urban planning and disaster response [3]. Similarly, citizens play a vital role in monitoring air quality and biodiversity by collecting valuable data through activities such as tracking butterfly populations or recording pollution levels, thus providing critical insights into environmental health and the effects of climate change [4], [5]. As these initiatives continue to gain momentum, data-driven methods are becoming integral to a

wide range of fields, from local governance to environmental monitoring, solidifying data processing and understanding as a central component of everyday decision-making.

With the growing involvement of citizens in data collection, analysis, and interpretation of information, the ability to process data, analyse results, and collaboratively generate insights has become a critical skill. However, the capacity to effectively use digital technologies to derive information varies significantly across different user groups, highlighting disparities in both digital literacy and proficiency. Generally speaking, *digital literacy* refers to the individual’s ability to understand and critically engage with digital information, while *digital proficiency* refers to technical competence to use digital tools effectively to perform tasks and solve problems [6]. Given that around 56% of people in Europe have basic digital skills and only about 28% have above basic digital skills [7], it is reasonable to expect a low level of satisfaction when interacting with digital technologies. Differences in digital skills across individuals can pose significant challenges to their ability to fully engage in data-driven initiatives. A lack of digital literacy and proficiency increases the risk of misinterpreting information, further adding to underutilization of valuable data or excluding less tech-savvy participants. These are considered as key factors that could hinder the overall effectiveness and inclusivity of citizen-based initiatives.

To address these aspects, our work draws on findings from an ongoing EU Innovation Action funded under the Horizon Europe framework that leverages active citizen participation in the whole data science lifecycle - data collection, processing, visualization, and analysis [8]. In this context, we investigate the complexities of digital literacy and proficiency across different geographical and social contexts, exploring how individuals interact with digital tools, the barriers they encounter, and the strategies required to strengthen their ability to engage meaningfully in data-driven tasks. Specifically, we evaluate participants’ technological readiness, data literacy, and proficiency with analytical tools, examining two distinct use cases: one utilizing a flexible and customizable data exploration and visualization platform, where users can define and configure their own data analytics workspace, and the other involving a predefined, modular data analytics environment with fixed interface configuration.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- **Digital Skills’ Impact on Citizen Participation:** A structured approach to understanding how varying levels of digital literacy and proficiency influence public participation in data-driven initiatives.
- **Impact of Data Analytics Platform Structures:** A systematic assessment of two types of data analytics platforms - flexible and customizable versus predefined and modular - to understand their impact on user engagement, data analysis, and decision-making.
- **Barriers and Solutions for Engagement:** A comprehensive set of concrete strategies to address the low digital literacy and proficiency in non-experts, such as training programs, motivation mechanisms, or support through newly emerging generative AI co-pilots.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work. Section III introduces our participants, user acceptance assessment methodology, and two data analytics platforms by outlining their differences. Section IV presents key findings derived from user interactions with these platforms. Section V critically discusses the implications of our findings, along the strategies to address identified barriers and enhance user engagement. Section VI concludes our contributions.

II. RELATED WORK

The topic of the digital skills gap among non-experts in citizen-based initiatives gained significant attention in recent years, particularly as digital technologies have become central to civic engagement and participatory decision-making [9]. Discussions on this topic often align with the broader concept of the *digital divide*, highlighting that access to technology alone is not enough [10]. Rather, the lack of digital literacy and proficiency presents a significant barrier that prevents individuals from effectively engaging in democratic processes and community-driven initiatives.

To illustrate the scale of the issue, Rodriguez-Hevíá et al. [11] explored the digital skills gap in the context of e-government adoption across European citizens. They emphasized that this gap is most pronounced among vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and low-income individuals, who often lack access to digital resources or struggle to develop the skills needed to navigate digital platforms effectively. To bridge this gap, Pade-Khene [12] argues that successful transfer of digital literacy knowledge and skills is crucial. Detlor [13] reinforces this perspective by examining the impact of digital literacy training initiatives led by community organizations. Their findings suggest that such programs are crucial for equipping individuals with the needed competencies.

Despite this recognition, much of the existing research continues to focus on the learning outcomes of citizen-based initiatives, particularly within citizen science experiments, and how participation in these initiatives contributes to the development of digital literacy skills [14], [15]. However, relatively few studies directly investigate the current state of digital competence among citizens and how it impacts their participation, leaving a critical gap in understanding of their

ability to effectively engage with digital technologies. This lack of insight may impede the development of truly inclusive participation frameworks, risking the exclusion of individuals with lower digital proficiency and limiting the diversity of voices and perspectives in citizen-based initiatives.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

As mentioned at the outset, this study draws on participants (n=17) from an ongoing EU Innovation Action, which promotes active public engagement in observing, sensing, and monitoring their living environments [8]. Representing five European pilot sites across diverse urban and rural settings in the Netherlands, Denmark, Italy, and the United Kingdom, these participants bring a broad spectrum of professional backgrounds, geographic contexts, and digital skills. This diversity provides a valuable foundation for assessing how these factors influence engagement with data-driven tools and shape patterns of participation. Specifically, our participant group spans multiple generations and professional backgrounds, including municipality and local community representatives, mobility experts, and social scientists. Comprising younger (20–35 years old, n=7) and middle-aged (36–55 years old, n=10) individuals with varying levels of digital literacy and proficiency, many of whom belong to Generations X and Y, this diverse composition enables a nuanced exploration of inter-generational differences in digital engagement and the influence of domain expertise on data interaction and analysis.

B. Use Cases

To assess the degree of participants’ acceptance level when interacting with different data analytics environments, we explore two distinct use cases, each offering a unique approach to data exploration and visualization. These use cases allow us to evaluate how varying levels of flexibility in tool’s structure influence participants’ ability to effectively navigate and engage with digital tools.

The first use case involves a flexible, customizable data analytics platform, where users have the freedom to configure their own data analytics workspace. Specifically, we utilize the capabilities of Apache Superset, an open-source business intelligence (BI) tool known for its versatility in creating dynamic dashboards and interactive data visualizations [16]. Superset supports a wide range of data sources and offers an intuitive, web-based interface for creating interactive dashboards, executing complex SQL queries, and generating insightful visualizations. With extensive customization options, users can tailor their analytics environment to fit their specific needs (see Figures 1 and 2). This high level of flexibility is expected to empower participants to explore different visualization techniques and interact with data dynamically. By employing this setup, we aim to assess how participants adapt to and navigate a highly configurable tool, while also recognizing that their roles may vary with some actively manipulating data and visualizations, others reviewing, defining requirements, and contributing to reflections on usability and relevance.

Fig. 1. Web-based Apache Superset platform highlighting its highly customizable canvas for flexible and intuitive graph creation.

Fig. 2. Web-based Apache Superset platform highlighting its highly customizable canvas space for interactive dashboard creation with drag-and-drop functionality, allowing users to easily tailor their workspace with visualizations like charts, tables, and number cards.

The second use case involves a predefined, modular web-based data analytics platform with fixed interface configurations, offering a structured approach to data exploration [17]. In contrast to highly flexible Superset setup, this environment minimizes potential complexity by limiting user customization, ensuring a consistent and user-friendly interface designed for ease of use and intuitive interaction. It builds on simple yet effective data representations, including an interactive map for geospatial data visualization, a line chart to illustrate temporal trends, a histogram for depicting the distribution of continuous variables, and a heatmap for analyzing time-based patterns within the dataset (see Figure 3). Additionally, key data quality metrics, descriptive statistics, and a tabular overview of the dataset are provided to enhance interpretability. By evaluating

this setup, we aim to understand how participants engage with a more rigid and structured platform, further investigating how its predefined structure influences their usability experience and insight generation capabilities.

C. User Acceptance Assessment

The user acceptance assessment is carried out through online video calls, which were recorded with a prior consent, as part of a series of onboarding and training sessions organized within the scope of the EU Innovation Action. Further user studies are carried out to evaluate the practical application and effectiveness of the tools in real-world usage scenarios. Participants' acceptance was evaluated through a combination of think-aloud protocols and action tracking by monitoring

Fig. 3. Modular web-based data analytics environment highlighting its structured interface. The layout includes visualizations such as a geospatial map, a line chart, a histogram, and a heatmap, but also data quality metrics, descriptive statistics, and a tabular data overview, available through a drop-down menu.

cursor movements to capture their real-time engagement patterns and cognitive challenges. As a result, we gathered only qualitative observations, rather than quantitative metrics. The assessment followed a structured process consisting of the following phases:

- **Onboarding & Training:** Participants were introduced to the tools and their features, ensuring they understood how to navigate and interact with each component effectively. This phase aimed to establish a baseline level of familiarity before proceeding to the free exploration step.
- **Free Exploration:** User acceptance was evaluated through a structured process that emulated a real-world data analytics workflow. This phase followed a common data exploration pipeline, including data loading, profiling, and insight generation. By allowing participants to engage with each stage, we assessed their ability to interact with the tools, interpret data, and derive insights.
- **Qualitative Feedback:** Participants were encouraged to provide real-time verbal feedback throughout the previous two phases. This phase helped identify challenges, usability concerns, and personal sentiments, offering deeper insights into participants' interaction with target data analytics platforms.

IV. RESULTS

A. Engagement with a Customizable Platform

Engagement with the Superset data analytics platform revealed significant challenges, already during the onboarding and training phase. Participants, regardless of age or professional background, encountered difficulties early on, struggling to navigate the platform's interface and customization workflow. As a result, most participants did not progress to the free exploration phase, feeling intimidated by the platform's

complexity and lacking the necessary skills for unsupervised development of their own data exploration workspace.

Municipality and community representatives from rural areas ($n=3$), in particular, faced greater challenges, often expressing confusion when switching between different tabs, transitioning between graph creation and the interactive dashboard development, and managing multiple visualization components. This was especially evident in the manual creation of data graphs, where they struggled to correctly assign values to the respective axes. Moreover, the SQL query functionality proved particularly daunting for all participants, as many were reluctant to engage with it due to their limited programming knowledge. The complexity of writing queries and understanding database structures created a significant barrier, making participants feel uncomfortable about executing tasks that required manual input. Additionally, participants representing municipality and community representatives ($n=6$) and social scientists ($n=4$) requested more guidance in interpreting data visualizations and trends, specifically asking for descriptive annotations to highlight key changes or patterns in the data (see Figure 4). This need for clearer explanations was consistent across all participant groups, regardless of their professional background or age, but was most pronounced among municipality and community representatives and social scientists, who expressed a greater need for context and clarity in understanding the visualized data.

B. Engagement with a Structured Platform

Engagement with the predefined, structured data analytics platform was somewhat less intimidating, as participants were not required to customize their own analytical workspace. Instead, during the onboarding and training phase, participants were guided through a predefined data analytics workflow that emulated a real-world data exploration scenario. This provided

Fig. 4. Example of a fully-customized dashboard in Superset illustrating the temporal development and geographic distribution of air quality data, where the lack of informational clarification and guiding mechanisms limits non-expert users' ability to accurately interpret the presented data.

a more streamlined approach to data exploration, ensuring that users could follow a clear, structured process while familiarizing themselves with the platform's core functionalities.

However, during the free exploration phase, more nuanced challenges began to surface. In particular, we observed that the concept of interactivity was not yet intuitive for many participants, especially for members of the social science group. They were more likely to perceive the visualization modules as static and were hesitant to engage in the interactive exploration of data. This perception led to adopting a more passive approach, where participants focused on simply viewing the data rather than actively manipulating the visualizations to uncover deeper insights.

Consistent with the observations from the Superset case study, participants were equally uncertain about the meaning of each data visualization module, particularly regarding the types of insights that could be derived from them. Additionally, by monitoring their actions through cursor movements, we observed that participants' attention was frequently directed to the wrong areas of the graph. This led to a general confusion during insight generation, as they often struggled to correctly match the value axes with the corresponding data visualizations, resulting in misinterpretation of the presented data. This occurrence was very prominent among municipality and community representatives. Lastly, as this data analytics platform also offers some limited user-defined customization options, these features were not well received across all user groups. Any request for user input was perceived as overwhelming, especially for participants who were already struggling with the platform's functionalities.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Key Insights from the User Acceptance Assessment

In the context of digital proficiency, our observations indicate that while, generally speaking, data analytics platforms with extensive customization options offer substantial versatility, they can also introduce significant challenges for non-expert users. The complexity introduced by a highly flexible interface may impede effective engagement, as users often struggle to navigate the multitude of features and configure the platform to meet their analytical needs. However, even without the added pressure of self-configuring the platform, as seen in the case of a more structured, predefined interface, participants still encountered difficulties in interaction. Furthermore, any requirement to engage with more advanced technical concepts, such as writing and executing queries, proved to be overwhelming for non-expert participants with limited technical background. In general, such requests are seen as a significant barrier, discouraging participants from even attempting to engage with the platform and thus should not be considered a core element of any future data-driven workflows in citizen-based initiatives.

In the context of digital literacy, difficulties in navigating and interpreting graphs were evident across both platforms and across the majority of user groups. Participants often struggled to correctly identify axes, associate data values with their corresponding data points, and interpret visual representations effectively. Furthermore, a lack of familiarity with key analytical concepts, such as trends, patterns, and outliers, significantly hindered their ability to derive meaningful insights, highlighting a critical gap in their data interpretation skills. While

tooltips were available to provide guidance, they did little to bridge this gap, suggesting that passive assistance alone is insufficient without deeper user support. These challenges not only contributed to user frustration but also significantly increased the learning curve. More importantly, this lack of clarity led to trust issues, as participants were questioning the reliability and accuracy of the information presented.

B. Strategies for Targeted User Support

To foster strong digital skills in non-experts, a continuous, adaptive, and accessible learning approach is essential. This approach should begin with a clear, user-friendly introduction that covers the basic features and purpose of digital tools and foundational analytical methods. Such learning materials should be designed to be flexible and adaptable to the diverse knowledge levels and learning capacities of participants. Furthermore, since most citizen-based initiatives operate across diverse geographical contexts, the inclusion of multilingual learning materials is equally important to eliminate any language barriers and ensure accessibility for all participants. Additional guiding mechanisms can be dynamically generated in real-time through data analysis, using interpretation support through prompt templates to guide users in extracting meaningful insights. Specifically, as data-driven platforms often lack personalized storytelling, generative AI could bridge this gap by processing visualization snapshots and metadata to create meaningful narratives, making descriptive analytics more accessible and insightful.

Initial learning stages should focus on building a solid foundation in basic data concepts, such as data types, simple visualizations, and basic statistical techniques. As participants progress, the learning experience should gradually introduce more complex data analysis concepts and advanced tool functionalities. Peer-to-peer learning should be further encouraged, fostering collaboration between experts and non-experts as they sit together to interpret charts, explain findings to one another, and co-produce insights. This structured progression would ensure a smooth transition, preventing learners from feeling overwhelmed. Throughout, the approach should prioritize consistent support and feedback mechanisms offered by the coordinators of the initiative, ensuring that participants are supported at every stage of their learning journey, thus promoting confidence and strengthening civic engagement. Lastly, the collaborative development of the involved technologies is equally important, with active participation from users throughout the process. This approach ensures that the design evolves based on their feedback and needs, fostering a deeper sense of purpose, ownership, and motivation, while improving the relevance and usability of the tools.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the critical role of digital literacy and proficiency in citizen-based initiatives, emphasizing how essential these skills are for fostering meaningful engagement and collaboration. While strong digital skills empower citizens by enhancing critical thinking, problem-solving abilities,

and fostering a deeper sense of purpose, our study showed that a lack of these skills can create significant barriers to civic engagement, resulting in a lack of trust in the process, increased frustration among participants, and discouraging participation in such initiatives. We propose targeted educational programs aimed at improving digital literacy and proficiency as a fundamental part of citizen-based initiatives. By implementing structured, adaptive learning approaches and offering accessible, user-friendly learning materials, these can help bridge the digital divide.

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